

1. Sample Information

Artificial seawater samples were analyzed for quantitative measurement of chlorophylls in the collected samples, chlorophylls are quantified using a method of HPLC.

2. Methods

2.1. Parameters

Column: Supelcosil LC318 C18 column (25 cm×4.6 mm×5 μm for computer modeling work and 10 cm×4.6 mm×5 μm for pigment isolations)

Flow rate: 1.0 mL/min

Mobile phase A: 70:30 (v/v) methanol, 28 mM aqueous TBAA, pH 6.5; Mobile phase B: methanol

The percentage of mobile phase was linear from 5% to 100% in 20 min.

2.2. Extraction Procedures

2.2.1. Work in a dimly lit environment and minimize evaporation of extraction solvent and light exposure during all steps. Label 15 mL polypropylene tubes with the sample numbers for the samples to be extracted.

2.2.2. Prepare an iced water bath for use once sample extraction begins.

2.2.3. Samples should remain in a -80°C freezer until the time of extraction, at which time, the selected samples are placed in a small cooler with dry ice.

2.2.4. Acetone to be used as the extraction solvent contains the vitamin E internal standard and is in the freezer, remove the storage bottle from the 15°C freezer and bring this solution to room temperature by placing the container with the solution in a bath of warm water until it is at room temperature.

2.2.5. Add 100 μL of deionized water at room temperature with a calibrated autopipet that measures no more than 1 ml, to each tube and place in a vial rack in a cooler. If it is known that the filter was blotted dry, add 200 μL of water.

2.2.6. Add 2.5 mL of 100% acetone using a calibrated bottle-top dispenser designed for organic solvents. Immediately cover the tube with Parafilm.

2.2.7. Place the cooler and tubes in the -25°C freezer for at least 30 minutes.

2.2.8. Remove the cooler and tubes from the freezer. For each tube, unwrap Parafilm, add a 25 mm GF/F sample filter, and immediately rewrap with Parafilm.

2.2.9. Repeat until all filters to be extracted that day are in tubes.

2.2.10. Place cooler and samples back in the -25°C freezer for 1 hour.

2.2.11. Completely macerate each filter using an ultra-sonic probe. The settings should approximate a duty cycle of 90% with an output level of 5. This procedure requires approximately 10s and can be timed by counting the pulses emitted by the probe. Prevent cavitation, pausing during sonication to push the filter slurry back down to the bottom of the tube if necessary. Partially submerge the tube in an ice and water bath during sonication to minimize heat accumulation. The condition of the sonicator tip should be periodically monitored and polished to yield a smooth surface, using very fine grade sandpaper (crocus sandpaper).

2.2.12. After processing each tube, cover with Parafilm again and return to the darkened ice bath (in the cooler).

2.2.13. Rinse off sonicator tip with 100% acetone and wipe with a Kimwipe between each sample.

2.2.14. After all samples have been processed, empty the cooler of ice and water and place the cooler and samples back in the -25°C freezer for 6 hours.

2.2.15. Remove the cooler, with samples, from the freezer. Filter each sample slurry through a 0.45 μm pore size PTFE syringe cartridge filter attached to a disposable plastic syringe. Collect the pigment extract in a glass scintillation vial with a foil-lined, labeled cap and immediately place the vial in a darkened environment.

- 2.2.16. After all samples have been filtered, vortex each sample extract and transfer approximately 500 µl of extract to an amber, labeled HPLC vial. Cap with a HPLC cap with a silicone/PTFE liner. Place vial in the pre-chilled temperature-controlled autosampler compartment of the HPLC. HPLC analysis should be started as soon as is practically possible. The unused extract is stored in the -15°C freezer until the HPLC analyses are successfully completed and data are reprocessed.
- 2.2.17. When all samples have been properly analyzed, record and transfer data to an excel spreadsheet for further calculations to determine the concentrations of agreed upon pigments of interest.